

Reputation: Launch

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Executive Summary

This document summarises the development strategy of the Reputation Management work package, understanding reputation management as an approach to identify female role models in innovation contexts starting with the women on the Advisory Board.

This document will explain the reputation approach through the evaluation criteria and the expectations and standards that emerge through this process, the profiles of the Advisory Board Gurus, as well as the accompaniment and co-creation activities with the Gurus and how the knowledge transfer between women Gurus and Ambassadors will be deployed.

This summary will be complemented by the visibility and accompaniment that will be deepened in the section of the WP6 Communication and Dissemination Plan.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Context and objectives from DoA¹ to reputation management

In line with initiatives such as the EU Prize for Women Innovators, Shemakes.eu promotes the emergence of excellence as a means of developing role models. However, the approach in Shemakes.eu has a collective dimension: the aim is to develop communities of excellence with multiple roles recognising the efforts, intentions and motivations of female leaders globally and locally. We also aim to encourage more women to become entrepreneurial leaders through innovation. We build on the concept of reputation as a mechanism for inducing a change in perception and behaviour in both social and business contexts.

In collective and collaborative groups, such as those of Shemakes.eu, reputation is built through practice and evidence as well as consensus; promoting the importance of specific community members reinforces the identity and shared values of the community. We see the importance of recognising women's efforts in transformation and advocating more women by sharing their experiences and leading innovation. In addition, we see reputation by sharing and shaping the community through mentoring, led by passionate women experts and entrepreneurs committed to their work. We believe and see that through programmes like Fabricademy and TCBL Labs, we can change the perspectives of many women and participants who can implement digitalisation, sustainability and entrepreneurship in a new generation, as promoted in Shemakes.eu. Thus helping to convey reputation at the collective level, i.e. the Labs, the Shemakes.eu network and, more broadly, the reputation of women in the T&C innovation context, the ultimate goal of the project.

WP4 aims to carry out Reputation Management to build a community of leading figures, role models, and emergent 'Ambassadors' with the precise aim to:

- Define a **Strategy** for common actions of e.g. brand management to enhance visibility and impact.
- Engaging Shemakes.eu **Advisors**: leading women figures in research, innovation and business, with an emphasis on the T&C sector.

¹ Description of Action of the Shemakes project

- Engaging **Gurus** within project staff for the different Learning Paths and Lab activities, especially for mentoring the Ambassadors and the 12 'transfer' Labs participating in the second phase of activities.
- Selecting **Ambassadors** from among the users of Learning Paths and Innovation Services, as transfer agents for the expansion of the network and testimonials of the Shemakes.eu experience.

WP4 definition

Reputation management is about appointing female role models at different levels, who will be key drivers and active members of the project, promoting the transformation process through innovation. Thus, we propose three groups Advisory Board, Gurus and Ambassadors, who will act in different perspectives tackling Shemakes' vision.

All reputation management members should be individuals committed to informing, inspiring, and supporting the Shemakes actions in their communities and networks. All women are invited to participate in this reputation strategy representing their personal and professional capacity and contributing to the transformation process through technological, societal and environmental innovation particularly in the textile and fashion industry.

WP4's strategy encompasses the participation and interaction of all three groups throughout the project. Thus, we want to reach the Shemakes audience at different levels in order to:

- convey the message of Shemakes
- reach diverse audiences from different perspectives
- give visibility and expand the project's networks
- receive feedback from the three groups throughout the project about their individual experience, interaction with their community and networks
- pivot the knowledge transfer process in collaboration with WP2 and WP3 between the post partner Labs and transfer Lab.
- enrich the Shemakes message through the Shemakes cycles.
- ensure that the project's reputation is built through the vision of innovation focussed on the work and user needs
- recognise entrepreneurial processes and encourage women to lead change in their community and networks.

Among other objectives that we will identify through the development and implementation of the reputation strategy, WP4 will support Advisors, Gurus and Ambassadors before, during and after their selection and participation in the project. The following graphic shows an overview of the reputation process and how the

three groups will accompany the whole project's strategy, deploying reputation actions until the project's end.

Figure 1 - Synthesis reputation management members [mural](#).

Advisors are leading figures in science, technology and industry, emphasising the T&C sector, guiding Shemakes.eu as a project and as a community with a shared goal. Shemakes coordination made their final selection in February 2021. They will support the project's development with a minimum of requirements during the whole project. For example, giving feedback to WP2 and WP3 and giving interviews starting from month six.

Gurus are members of project partner staff, leading the educational and Lab activities within their local communities. They show how to practice gender parity as community entrepreneurs. Guru's input plan starts in the PM3 and should be aligned with WP2 and WP3, reporting the process's toolkits activities and how it impacts the participant's engagement. Together with the WP leaders, they will supervise and give feedback on the reputation management strategy, particularly in the Ambassadors and transfer Lab selection and mentoring.

Ambassadors are participants in the Shemakes.eu Lab activities. They are singled out for their ability to understand the methods and tools and communicate them to others. Ambassadors from the first phase will be selected between October and December 2021 to participate in residencies at the transfer Labs at the beginning of

2022, bringing the knowledge and best practices from the partner Labs' to the transfer Labs. They will help to launch the second phase. In the second phase, partners and transfer Labs will select 18 Ambassadors. WP4 will support the selection, participation and networking process to guarantee the impact of the Shemakes message.

Visibility in the reputation strategy is widely promoted through the communication actions included in WP6, leveraging, above all, social media as a means of embedding the new values co-created in the Shemakes.eu Lab contexts as new norms of gender behaviours and practices. As figure 1 shows, the visibility of the activities (e.g. interviews, videos) from the Advisory Board to Gurus and to the Ambassadors, will be reproduced and promoted through the WP6.

A more detailed description of the actions is summarised in table 1.

Timeline

Table 1 - Timeline of involvement of the Gurus, Ambassadors and transfer Labs

Tasks	Date (Timing)
Gurus	M4 - M24
Start of the Learning Paths and Innovation Services	April 2021
Profile map for Gurus	Middle March 2021
Activities of Gurus (first iteration)	April-September 2021
Ambassadors	M10 - M24
Selection process for Ambassadors	October 2021
Appointment of Ambassadors	October-November 2021
Start of the pitch-session to select /confirm the Ambassadors	November-December 2021
Ambassadors replicating activities in the transfer Labs	January-June 2022 (Approx)
Transfer Labs	M12-24
Open Call transfer Labs	November - December 2021

1.2 Methodology

During the three months, different activities were carried out to develop a global vision of the project, understand the gender vision, the Learning Paths' objectives and the Innovation Services to adapt the reputation strategy to the Shemakes DoA objectives. The reputation strategy approach was mainly created through documentary research. As the leader of the WP4, MATRIX has emphasised integrating the reputation strategy from the gender vision (TIG), the innovation methodology and the co-creation of the WP2 Learning Paths and WP3 Innovation Services. These first actions were enriched with all partners' meetings, especially the Labs, and close contact with WP6 communication and dissemination. In parallel, local meetings of the internal MATRIX with the communications director, gender vision team and innovation team were also held.

The following is a list of the events in which feedback was taken to develop the reputation strategy with their corresponding co-creation tables.

1.3 Synthesis of Activities Carried Out

Table 2 - Synthesis of Activities Carried Out.

Date	Meetings	Who	Link documentation
4.01.2021	Pre-meeting Brainstorming I	TCBL,TIG, MATRIX	Link
11-01.2021	WP2-WP3-WP4 vision meeting preparation	IAAC, WAAG, MATRIX	Link
15.01.2021	SU kick-off WP2 Brainstorming I and II	All SU partners	Link Link
29.01.2021	Internal meeting MATRIX Reputation	Head Communication, Head Woman engagement, Head Innovation	Link
5.02.2021	Meeting Gender Vision TIG exchange gender vision and innovation ecosystem	TIG MATRIX	further conversation after Theory of change workshop

Date	Meetings	Who	Link documentation
12.02.2021	Exchange ideation communication	MATRIX, FLOD	further details in the communication and visibility content section
26.02.2021	Preparation Advisory board presentation and questions	TCBL, FLOD, MATRIX	further details in the AB first meeting
2.02.2021	Meeting Advisory Board	TCBL, MATRIX , FLOD, Advisory Board (six members)	
5.03.2021	Mentoring platform Spot via makesense	MATRIX, MAKE	further details in the Mentorship section
23.02.2021 10.03.2021	Meeting IAAC -MATRIX	Exchange Learning Path and fab practices into reputation management	Link MIRO
02.02.2021	SC meeting	TCBL, IAAC, FLOD, MATRIX, WAAG	Link MIRO
05.02.2021	SU Labs meeting 2	All Labs except WAAG, MATRIX	Link MIRO
12.02.2021	SU Labs meeting 2	All Labs except WAAG, MATRIX	Link MIRO
19.02.2021	SU Labs meeting 3	All Labs, MATRIX	Link MIRO
26.02.2021	SU Labs meeting 4	All Labs, MATRIX	Link MIRO
03.03.2021	SU Labs meeting 5	All Labs, MATRIX	Link MIRO
03.03.2021	Alignment with TCBL	TCBL + WP2 task leaders	Link MIRO
10.03.2021	SU Labs meeting 6	All Labs	Link MIRO

It is essential to highlight that the development of the reputation strategy needs the inputs of the first three work packages to fulfil a proposal that encompasses all the actions close to the Shemakes community expectations. Therefore, in the first three months, the reputation strategy is focussed on identifying the needs and motivations of the Shemakes audience through the co-creation tools MIRO and MURAL. The

following section describes the process that has been carried out through the actions step by step.

Step 1. From gender vision to reputation strategy

The reputation management process follows four main steps in Shemakes. In the first step, WP4 focuses on the selection and structure of the Advisory Board's work and the identification of opportunities for women in innovation ecosystems. To understand the roles of women in new entrepreneurship scenarios and how to identify women leaders in the textile and fashion industry, we start by recognizing what drives women to leadership. Therefore, the reputation management work package stimulates innovation in a cross-cutting way from the innovation ecosystem (WPI) by understanding the best practices of the Learning Paths (WP2) to the Innovation Services (WP3).

Figure 2 - First step reputation management gender vision, Innovation and Advisory Board.

Step 2. Understanding the role models/profiles

The second step starts with the reflection of how we can identify the role models in women experts in the fields of STEAM, fashion & textile industry and entrepreneurship within Shemakes. From this reflection, we simultaneously researched opportunities for women in innovation ecosystems. We gathered the input of women experts working in partner Labs to provide a comprehensive overview of their needs, motivations and frustrations and to recognise the profile and competences of female makers to deliver the innovation standards across the Shemakes project.

Figure 3 - Second phase reputation management approach: profiles.

For this purpose, we co-created the profile map to understand the individual ecosystem of women who have been instrumental in inspiring the project proposal (Figure 3, more details will be given in the section profile map). We proceeded to carry out the profile map of the Gurus and general Shemakes actors and future participants or potential Ambassadors.

Step 3. How to support the process

Gurus Framework

In the third step we focussed on mapping some of the people who might be the future Gurus with whom we will work in the next WP4 period from April to September 2021. We proposed a set of activities based on the information from the Guru mapping, to support their collaborative process and print and ensure a “user-centred” innovation approach.

We consider it essential to integrate these activities (Figure 4) in the project's development. However, we advise that these activities are co-created with the Learning Paths and Innovation Services to ensure their success and avoid overlapping content between WPs. This process of planning and co-creative work with the Gurus will prepare the project's second cycle. The aim of the Guru's plan is mentoring and guidance of the Ambassadors and the transfer Labs. Thus, WP4 is aligned with the iterative Shemakes process and with the outputs of WP2 and WP3. We will start in the second cycle of the project with the Ambassador's application process.

Figure 4 - Gurus Framework.

Ambassadors Framework

In the second cycle of the project (start 2022), we expect the Gurus to lead the Ambassadors' activities and mentoring together with WP4. In this way, the Ambassadors will be the new mediators and top leaders between local and global communication and partly in charge of knowledge transfer from the Shemakes practices to the transfer Labs. In collaboration with WP2, WP3 and WP6, we propose a series of activities to promote their participation in Shemakes, particularly in their residency in the transfer Labs and in the community to accomplish the expected outreach.

Figure 5 - Ambassador’s Framework.

Step 4. Visibility, communication and sharing content

Figure 6 - Visibility, communication and sharing content.

Communication actions are essential for the visibility of reputation management and will strategically support the development of WP4 in all its phases. For this reason, WP4 and WP6 task leaders are in charge of gathering, processing, and disseminating relevant information on role models, promoting the Advisory Board's

actions, the Gurus and the Ambassadors. This process should convey a clear message promoting the diversity and inclusion in the communication of Shemakes' values. With the support of WP6, we aim to support the process of digitisation and documentation of the results of three groups such as interviews, videos, and graphic material to produce formats that encourage the active participation of the audience and bring the message of Shemakes to the local and global community. Our final expectation is that these communication and content sharing processes (Figure 6) will be able to reach a wide audience. This will help the exchange of experiences and the creation of new networks in innovation ecosystems.

Figure 7 – Reputation Management Methodology.

2. Shemakes Approach to reputation

2.1 From SU Innovation Gender Vision to Reputation Strategy

The overall layer of the project focuses on expanding women's opportunities in innovation contexts. Thus, the reputation strategy considers it extremely important that the innovative approach is developed across all work packages, particularly in the WPI Opportunities Ecosystem, WP2 Learning Paths and WP3 Innovation Services packages. We call this the transversal innovation approach. It means the reputation strategy addresses the communication of Shemakes' message and identifies the opportunities and needs of the role models, supporting the processes we will undertake with reputation management members and encouraging more women to engage in innovation processes and gender inclusiveness. In this way, WP4 seeks to establish best practices in innovation as a mechanism to guarantee reputation actions.

First desk research addressed the following topics that will be further elaborated in WPI Ecosystem Opportunities and, in particular, the Innovation Methodology:

- Women in entrepreneurship processes
- What brings women into leadership roles
- Barriers for women in STEAM education
- How we can identify role models in Shemakes

For "user-centred" innovation work, it is essential to know the "users'" real perspectives and needs. It means that to develop best practices and to fill possible ecosystem gaps it is crucial to know what women and the actors in the sector really need and want, what resources they need to be innovative, what they lack and what they like and also what the market, business and society needs.

For an initial mapping of needs, but also to kick-start the ecosystem mapping, a first set of questions has been developed to complement past and future workshops:

- What do we already know about the target group, what information is missing?
- Who are important stakeholders?
- What are the needs of the target group, what are the needs of the project partners towards an innovation ecosystem/methodology?

- Which activities, offers, training, tools are already in use? What was successful so far? What worked best? (WP2 and WP3)
- What are the remaining needs/gaps to fill?
- What processes could help the Labs and the women to expand their professional capacities and innovation work?
- What does innovation mean to Labs and women?
- What are existing and possible KPI to measure the goals?

From the meeting between TIG and MATRIX (table 2) and the Theory of Change workshop, we have seen that the above research is strongly interconnected with the elements of the WPI Opportunities Ecosystem and WP5 Evaluation and Assessment of Shemakes. It is expected that these activities will be expanded together with all partners, and further details will be given in the following deliverables with the subtask Innovation Methodology and close collaboration with WPI and WP5.

First dialogues about role models in Shemakes

To start the dialogues with the Labs and understand how to approach the role models, we first did it internally in MATRIX by asking about the development of the current projects. Some of the ideas that came out of the internal Matrix meeting were:

- Motivation leads to taking an initiative.
- Women can shape networks through teamwork, developing bonds that allow for the sustainability of their work.
- Accept differences and embrace gender diversity.
- Promoting women who have been represented with their work in school laboratories encourages the participation of more young female makers in STEAM Education e.g. ZDI-Heldinnen (Helmerdig, 2021) ('zdi-Gurus',2021).

To start with identifying the first criteria of the role models, we met with the six Labs.

We asked about their activities with questions about:

- how to identify the role models? their values, skills, and vision
- how the Labs identify role models and recognise motivated participants and how the Labs activities have helped the audience enhance their professional and personal aspirations (Figure 8)
- how to provide continuity to the SU activities to accumulate experiences and knowledge?
- how to motivate the SU entrepreneurs to keep the community active?

Figure 8 – Role models (miro).

Some of the notes from the first meeting discussed the definition and identification of role models. This overview can be found in table 3.

Table 3 – Overview definition and identification of role models

Lab	notes & comments
IAAC	<p>Fabricademy is a learning-by-doing programme, and it is a challenge to test the theory so that it is synchronised and makes sense in its practices.</p> <p>There is no process for identifying potential role models. They could be targeted but not processed.</p> <p>It could be a good approach if each Lab can identify potential role models to choose from in a selection process.</p>
LEON	<p>Girls seek their own opportunity to achieve their purposes, in this particular case, coding. Just as families provide girls with opportunities to pursue their interests, Labs could enter the game to offer learning opportunities that are not available to families and initiate new interest groups where other girls can be added.</p> <p>Girls are fascinated about the activities and prototype that they have in the Labs but they don't know how to achieve the results. Therefore the role of the mentor and the accomplishment project are essential to achieve the goals of the kid.</p>
REDU	It is also an activity to teach children to work in groups and to lead their team

Lab	notes & comments
	processes. This can be added to the skills and competencies that can be fostered in Shemakes.
ONLF	Enriching the diversity in the mixed male and female groups also helps the process of having equal roles.
MAKE	Many skills can be developed through the MAKE curriculum. Those can be applied in the consolidation of leadership competencies. e.g. emotional intelligence, how to build their speech and avoid violent communication among others. supporting, mentoring, training, and exchange matchmaking events help the process to succeed in the expert role (session mentoring and networking).
WAAG	To start the identification of role models we can take the example of the first women who are leaders of Shemakes. We can take the values that have made them successful in the Fabricademy project or representative in their areas of work. It is essential to identify the benefits of working with female role models and cover those characteristics in which males are characterised, e.g. risk-takers.

To deepen this exercise, we co-created the profile map with WP2 and WP3 which will be explained below.

These first dialogues led us to a structure for the analysis of the individual spheres of the context of people close to the Labs and the project, which could potentially be members of the reputation strategy at different levels as Gurus or Ambassadors through the tool called profile map.

Profile map

The development of the profile map was based on the persona map format. However, the persona map illustrates a fictitious person and tries to empathise with the user to understand their needs, frustrations, opportunities and challenges (Dam/Siang 2021) .

In this case, the profile map was transformed to be filled in by our real Gurus and potential participants (Ambassadors) to meet the requirements of Shemakes. This map was co-created together with the six Labs and in particular with the WP leaders of the WP2 Learning Paths and WP3 Innovation Services.

We adapted the content of this map from an individual sphere starting with gender and personality. Gender is thus not just a personality characteristic but is constructed and continuously negotiated across an individual's personality, interactions with others, communities and culture (Risman & Davis, 2013). In the

context of Shemakes, we embrace the diversity of characters and foster the identification of personalities, thus contributing in a better participation of an individual in a group.

Figure 9 – Profile map (mural).

We also asked about **personality** as part of the roles that women can have in a team or the roles that women can assume in leadership, an important position related to a woman's behaviour in a situation adapting to the 16 personalities and 8 types of leader found in the Jungian types (NERIS, 2021) and adapted for our purpose.

As a leader I can be...

- Entrepreneur, Adventurer, Facilitator, Entertainer, Inventor, Visionaire,
- Executer, Teacher, Architect, Defender, Thinker and Translator.

Figure 10 - Extract from a profile map, "My personality - As a leader, I can be..."

We asked women to fill in the personality and add the percentage of different personalities, or better called soft skills, that characterise them. Figure 10 shows the mapping of the profile of a female CEO. It is interesting to see how all the skills converge to shape her personality, into her personal and professional competencies, especially in this leadership position.

We consider **motivation** and goals (My next big challenge in life is...) expressed through challenges and how these issues may relate to the **frustrations**, which are essential elements in interpersonal success, and how they may benefit both men and women's work and performance.

Skills and Interests are mentioned in the map as a part of the existing offer and topics related to Fabricademy and the TCBL Labs. The skills are drawn from competencies developed in the Fabricademy and the interests are the main agendas topics of the programme. This segment also directly relates to the readiness to enter a market and the interest and willingness to learn and participate in the Learning Paths and Innovation Services.

Skills: I'm particularly good at:

- **Fashion & Textile** (Traditional fashion skills - pattern making, sewing, weaving, knitting, etc.)
- **Graphic & Image** (Creative art direction, conceptual branding, photoshop, illustration skills)
- **Prototype & industrial products** (Turning design ideas into process of manufacturing real-life products)
- **Concept & Business** (Tools for growing ideas into Business e.g. design thinking, innovation strategies)
- **Education & research** (Academic & non academic, research & development)
- **Creative co-design** (Creating best practices for collaborative work support a growing community teamwork)

Interest: I'm particularly interested in:

- **Sustainability** (Circular fashion, bacterial -natural textile dyeing, grown materials, biomaterials, textile composites)
- **Fashion tech** (E-textiles Wearables, Soft Robotics, Skin Electronics)
- **Industry 4.0** (Laser cutting, 3D printing, Open Source Hardware, IoT, Computational Couture)
- **Entrepreneurship** (Project management, business development, open innovation, capital adventure)
- **Mentoring** (Teaching mentoring & consulting practices through textiles)
- **Health Tech** (Design for all, disabilities, inclusive universal design)
- **Arts & Crafts** (Performative, costume, sound, installation, exhibition design & creative economies)

Outcomes (your innovation) are related to their goals and their contributions and initiatives that they have already consolidated, making them proud to have achieved them. Also connected with the **opportunities** to explore during the project that can be achieved in a period (I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...)

Finally, we asked about some of the **textile and clothing industry's point of view**, perceptions and their thought processes through women in leadership. Also, what media(channels) are meant for women and how these help existing processes that might describe their inspirational source and can enrich the input of Shemakes activities. in the following points:

- Opportunities / wishes
- Barriers / needs
- Trends

It is worth highlighting that this is an adaptation of the criteria to help identify the women's profiles and the barriers and opportunities for entrepreneurship at different levels and in diverse groups of Shemakes.

Although this profile map exercise was carried out individually to protect the privacy of the participants, it is expected that these dialogues will be shared and continued, mainly with the Gurus, in the following months to strengthen the strategy and facilitate the transfer of knowledge between the Gurus, Ambassadors and transfer Labs. This process will address the exchange from the identification of the individual needs to collaborative opportunities.

3.Reputation management members

3.1 Advisory Board

Advisory board is a group of nine women selected from the beginning of the project to contribute to their vision and enrich the Shemakes guidelines. They will participate in the Shemakes strategy giving feedback to the proposals of the WP2 Learning Paths and WP3 Innovation Services. The Advisory Board will support the Ambassadors' selection to see their work and ensure that the Shemakes values are maintained and carried through the project.

Role and activities in Shemakes

The Advisory Board involves a group of 9 prominent figures who have achieved success in a range of fields related to innovation and the textile and clothing industry. This is intended to somewhat echo the EU strategy for assigning the Prize for Women Innovators, which “celebrates the women entrepreneurs behind game-changing innovations”.²

We have devised a work plan that gets the greatest value out of their observations and insights. The steps are as follows:

1. Our first step was to hold a 90-minute video conference meeting at the end of February 2021 with all project partners and Advisory Board members, mainly to get to know each other and share our views on the project's objective. Here, we presented the project goals and approach and from there gathered strategic input for the project overall. A report on the outcomes of this meeting is in the following section.
2. Following that, we will be issuing a regular series of video interviews, asking our Advisory Board members to participate in at least one of these events on a mutually agreed date. We expect this to require about an hour.
3. At the end of the first pilot phase we will hold a second series of video conference meetings (between October and November 2021) to review presentations of the work from the starting network of 6 Shemakes.eu Labs in the 8-18, 18-25, and 25+ age groups, as well as the three Lab-to-Lab projects.

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/prizes/eu-prize-women-innovators_en

This may require more than one hour-long slot. Here, we'll be interested in the Advisory Board's opinions on the work presented and any strategic advice coming from that. On the basis of our conversations and other factors, we will be selecting 12 Ambassadors from among the participants to act as Ambassadors to the 12 new Labs joining for the second phase of piloting.

4. At the end of the second pilot phase (between July and September 2022), we will repeat the same review process, only this time we'll be looking at the work of 18 Labs. If so agreed with the Advisory Board members, project partners may on this occasion carry out a pre-selection of the results to be presented, so as to limit the amount of time that will be required. Here, we'll be again interested in the Advisory Board's opinions on the work presented and focus on the prospects for post-project sustainability as well. On the basis of our conversations and other evidence, we will be selecting 18 from among the participants to present their work at the Final Conference.
5. The project's final conference will be held between October and November 2022, likely in Nimes (FR), in conjunction with the [#TCBL_2022 event](#). All Advisory Board members will be invited to participate with travel expenses covered, and will all be considered as possible speakers.

Selection of Advisory Board members

The selection process for the Advisory Board members was carried out in the project proposal and pre-launch phases and finalised in the first months of the project in view of the first teleconference in M2.

The number of nine members was agreed upon as being large enough to represent a diversity of backgrounds and viewpoints while sufficiently limited to allow for a manageable group. Our desire was to include:

- A mix of those directly involved in the T&C industry and others engaged more broadly in innovation and possible futures.
- A mix of different activities within the T&C industry, such as design, textile production, garment production, etc.
- A mix of organisational profiles including research, university, business, and associations ([quadruple helix](#) model).
- At least one finalist or awardee of the EU Women in Innovation prize.
- A minimum of geographical distribution representative of European diversity.

Through formal and informal contacts from project partners, the following list of persons was identified.

Table 4 - List of members of the Advisory Board.

N.	Name	Description
1	Mara Balestrini	CEO of Ideas for Change, an innovation agency at the intersection of civic technology, data, co-creation and Action Research (ES).
2	Rebecca Earley	Co-founder of the Centre for Circular Design at Chelsea College of Arts, University of the Arts London (UK).
3	Anna Fiscale	Cooperativa Sociale Quid (sustainable fashion with textile deadstock, IT) , Finalist of the EU Prize for Women Innovators
4	Silvia Brandi	The CEO of Atlas of the Future , a non-profit online resource of hope mapping and raising the profiles of innovative, future-focussed projects. (ES/UK)
5	Marte Hentschel	CEO of Sqetch (DE/NL), a T&C brand-manufacturer community and matchmaking platform with over 25,000 subscribers.
6	Aurélie Mossé	Director of the Soft Matters group at Ensad Lab (FR) , mixing vanguard techniques with traditional craft.
7	Gabriela Macoveiu	Gabriela Macoveiu, director of RDA NE (RO), the Regional Development Agency managing ERDF funds for NE Romania.
8	Amber Jae Slooten	Creative director at The Fabricant (NL), working with the body, animation and digital fashion design.
9	Daniela Toccafondi	Director of Prato Futura (IT), industrial think tank for Europe's largest textile production district.

In terms of matches to the selection criteria mentioned above, we can note the following:

Table 5 - Matching of Advisory Board members to selection criteria.

Name	Field	T&C activity	Organisation	Country
Mara Balestrini	Innovation	-	Consultancy	ES
Rebecca Earley	Circular Economy	Design	University	UK
Anna Fiscale	T&C	Upscaling (re-use)	Social enterprise	IT
Silvia Brandi	Futures	-	NGO	ES/UK
Marte Hentschel	Production matchmaking	On-line Services	SME	DE
Aurélie Mossé	Research	Fabrics	University	FR

Name	Field	T&C activity	Organisation	Country
Gabriela Macoveiu	Regional policy	-	Regional Development Agency	RO
Amber Jae Slooten	Fashion	Digital fashion	Business	NL
Daniela Toccafondi	Textiles	Textiles production	Industrial Association	IT

Report on the first Advisory Board meeting

The first meeting with the Advisory Board was held from 16.00–17.30 on February 3rd, 2021, via GoToMeeting. Six of the Advisory Board members attended the videoconference:

- Mara Balestrini
- Rebecca Earley
- Marte Henschel
- Valeria Valotto (on behalf of Anna Fiscale)
- Silvia Brandi
- Daniela Toccafondi

Following a round of self-presentations of the Advisory Board members attending and a presentation of the project goal and objective, there was a round table discussion chaired by Caterina Ailiesei. The debate focussed on three questions:

1. In the move towards sustainable fashion, how is the role of women affected (or conversely, how is the move towards sustainability affected by women)?
2. In what ways do you think innovation can contribute to bridging the gender gap?
3. What values do you think are essential to build in the next generation of girls and women in the Textile and Clothing sector?

Those who were not able to attend or who had to leave early sent written contributions, so the following synthesis of the main contributions, anonymised for purposes of privacy, can be said to reflect the contributions of all members.

- Considering that the textile industry is one of the more polluting industries in the world, affecting climate change and the environmental disaster, there is a great opportunity for women to lead the change by acting on the fashion system. Women are known to be more likely to adopt greener behaviours and products than men. It seems plausible that the more women reach leadership positions in fashion the more likely it is that fashion will become more sustainable. In turn, if this happens and effects are positive, women will be

responsible for achieving positive outcomes, which will strengthen their leadership and hopefully attract others to follow on the example. This is a great opportunity for women to act on one of the most critical sectors for climate change.

- Although there is now a lot of effort towards Circular Economy, it is still unclear how this topic is going to unfold and become mainstream industrial and economic practice. We have to rethink everything, beginning from the designing of the new clothes. In addition, there is the impact of Covid. For instance, smart working is something that changes our way of life; it may be trending now, but it will surely have a permanent impact. And there are many things that will change, with an effect on how we choose, wear and produce clothes.
- Young women aged 18 to 24, studying to enter the sector, need to understand how their attitudes and behaviours as consumers and lovers of fashion are equally as important as their technical and design skills. They need to see themselves not just through their role in the industry but also to be influential in how they live and the kind of fashion they're interested in. At a broader level and at all ages, we shouldn't disassociate life choices from professional identities in the industry. For instance, the family can play a significant role in shaping values – “we live to be dressed”, our tastes and behaviours affect others' lives. We can start with education in the family and then build on that in the schools. Boys and girls are consumers just as much as their elders; they too can preserve resources, promote gender equality and appreciate beauty and usefulness.
- Southern Europe is somehow less prepared than Northern Europe to focus on and address the challenge of climate change. Instead, there seems to be an effort to make it look like all Europe is at the same level. On the other hand, women are more active than men in addressing the changes needed towards a more sustainable fashion system; the urgency of the situation is an opportunity for women to take more leadership, even in less receptive contexts. There are cultural differences and there are probably countries where there is a greater need for pioneers to change the world. Young women have the power to connect differently and maybe there is a crowd power which helps change the general mentality more quickly than we expect. Take [Fashion Revolution](#) as an example, totally unexpected. In the past, it has been difficult, but the younger generation have tools, attitudes, and collective support across borders and internationally that will help them to be role models in a transformative society.
- Today's young women are less limited than before by gender or location when looking for professional role models and business opportunities, at least in some countries. On the other hand, these young women are more than ever seeking for purpose in their professional path. So now there's a disconnect between a career path that is success-driven, linked to technology, engineering and entrepreneurial mindsets, and a different path which involves

working with people, being socially driven, purpose driven, impact driven. We need more role models and success stories of female leaders that prove that it is possible to bridge this kind of paradox: good at business but also impacting not only the textile industry but their communities as well.

- New technologies are helping young women to have voices and platforms and to step up. The biggest challenge is to keep that voice confident and visible. Young girls speak to all the world, but as they go into different periods of their life, with adolescence or for other reasons, they lose confidence, their tone of voice changes and the way they communicate changes. Now, technology is really affecting that, giving more ability and more platform to women in different stages, but especially for the younger generations to catalyse debate and change through social media. Confidence and recognition of skills is central to the process. Women need to trust and understand their sensitivity as an asset but equally important is that this is recognised by men. Essential values lie in perseverance, a true sense of cooperation and in respecting the inner self and boundaries. New media can thus help young women to express these values, becoming a powerful tool to define strong leadership and agency in innovation.
- It is unclear if it is innovation that is instrumental to bridging the gender gap or if we need to bridge the gender gap in order to have a more innovative ecosystem. Most innovation can become a driver in bridging the gender gap, but it depends very much on how the innovation is developed and appropriated. As women we do bring a different outlook and insight and expertise in re-defining power systems and ecosystems. This involves developing a culture to work, plan and implement together. Cooperation is also needed to encourage dialogue along design/production/sales components of the value chain. And women are known to be strong collaborators.
- Innovation is dependent on creativity, and diversity as well as collaboration. Decision makers know that to achieve highly innovative teams they need to include more women and people with diverse backgrounds. Plus, to retain talent, they have to improve the conditions of women, matching salaries and supporting the reconciliation between family and work. On the other hand, much innovation is needed to design ways to overcome the gender gap as this is a social, economic, political, and cultural issue.
- We need to create a positive image of the textile and clothing industry to attract creative and inspired young women who can go on to become leaders and role models. The T&C value proposition includes working with innovative technologies and materials, using creativity and respect, exploring ways to soothe, protect and warm the body, and of course allow for personal expression and bringing beauty into our lives.

Insights to feed into project activities

From the above discussion, it is possible to extract specific recommendations for Shemakes project activities in the first year.

- a. **Shemakes should situate itself firmly in the movement for sustainable fashion as a means to address climate change.** There has already been a decision to dedicate activities to circular and sustainable fashion, but this can be made more explicit. If the challenge of climate change is an opportunity for women to take a leading role, then Shemakes must become a vehicle for that kind of empowerment.
- b. **Shemakes needs to explore the new post-Covid scenarios for work, life and play.** This will determine both changes in consumption patterns (already visible in the shift towards leisurewear) as well as changes in workplace practices and cultures. Shemakes has the opportunity to influence the paths that both will take.
- c. **Shemakes participants need to gain awareness that they are both within the industry and consumers of industry products.** The choices made in what to design and produce and how are important, but it is equally important that women adopt fair and sustainable lifestyles, with consumption choices coherent with their work goals.
- d. **Shemakes needs to convey the value of blending business viability with purposeful innovation.** Having an impact on society and the environment needs to be a driving goal for Shemakes activities, but impact also requires that products and processes make business sense. This will be particularly important when developing new business concepts and working with existing T&C enterprises.
- e. **Shemakes should not only build capacity, but also use social media to empower girls and women to build confidence and communicate their beliefs and skills.** The Shemakes communication strategy will play an important role in providing the framework to vehicle these messages, but participants also need to play an active part in communication actions. Shemakes Gurus and Ambassadors can play an important role in this regard.
- f. **Shemakes needs to better understand the dynamics linking different forms of innovation to gender equity.** This includes both the degree to which innovation leads to equity as compared to increased equity engendering innovation. In addition, these dynamics may vary according to different kinds of innovation: technical innovation in processes and materials, innovation in means of communication, social innovation in working methods, societal innovation for more just and sustainable democracies.
- g. **Shemakes should also monitor the influence of geographical and cultural differences on innovation dynamics.** The territories both within and beyond EU borders that will be hosting Shemakes activities may display different levels of awareness and readiness of the different issues being addressed, from climate change and gender parity to social and technical innovation. While diversity can

be a resource for Shemakes goals, different situations will present different barriers and opportunities that will need to be taken into account.

Next steps

We are currently collecting information from the Advisory Board members in order to be able to promote their profiles as Shemakes role models through our communication strategy. This will include the production of:

- A graphic for distribution on social media based on information about the advisor's career and personal preferences.
- A short video using images and photos e.g. from childhood, at work, etc. with information from her CV.
- Preparation of the video interview (see below).

In addition, the video interview series will be launched at the end April, and we are currently organising the sequence and the layout for these, to be live-streamed and also documented on the website.

According to our work plan, the next plenary event will take place likely in November 2021 to review the results of the first phase of experimentation with the Shemakes Labs.

3.2 Gurus

Gurus are members of the six Labs who have a high level of expertise not only in their skills, but through their experience and initiatives, and have been recognised and identified as leaders in their Labs and communities. They will help the exchange of the local and global community mentoring through their expertise and the best practices of Learning Paths and Innovation Services. In accompanying the WP leaders, Gurus will advocate responsible and disruptive innovation.

Guru's role

The Gurus' main task is to maintain contact with their Lab and community and generate exchange between them. General goals during their activities at this stage are:

- Engaging with participants that can become Ambassadors.
- Engaging with possible candidate labs and staging the labs to enable them for Shemakes activities. Mentor targets of the Learning Paths when necessary.
- Supporting participants with tools and equipment used in the Learning Paths.

- Facilitating the understanding of the roles of the Ambassadors as part of the reputation management system, the Gurus are expected to participate in innovation-driven activities to deploy the project's innovation methodology.

The above list is not exhaustive and will be further developed after the first step is completed.

One member of each partner lab is selected to become a Guru, thus articulating the process of Shemakes reputation management. Gurus will help in mentoring the process of Ambassadors and transfer labs. Three Gurus will come from Learning Paths and the other three from Innovation Services. The six experts will be involved in the next months (from April to September 2021) to start the planning of vision and engagement of Gurus during Shemakes.

Selection

The Gurus are female members of the partner lab team and should have mastered the hands-on activities and have had experience working with the target groups of Shemakes and key partners. They are able to advise the transfer labs. For this reason, a prior selection has been made during the meetings with the co-creation with the lab. Each lab should consider who has the availability and disposition to be a Shemakes Guru. In the following table you can find a prior selection of the Gurus. Changes can be considered to this list.

Table 6 - List of potential members of Gurus

Name	Field	SU activity	Organisation	Country
Anastasia Pistofidou	Architecture	Textile technology and sustainability	IAAC	ES
Nuria Robles	Mechanical Engineering	STEM education	LEON	ES
Cristina Olivotto	Physics Science Education and Communication	Fab Lab Manager	ONLF	CH
-	Political Sciences Entrepreneur	Trainings for young entrepreneurs	MAKE	FR
Beatriz Sandini	Business Administration	Fashion Business management Brand of sustainable fashion Cor-Botanicals	WAAG	NL

Andrea Sofronea	Performing & Theoretical Arts Fashion	Zero Waste shop Project support at Mai bine NGO	REDU	RO
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Since there is already a Gurus members proposal, we will identify different aspects of their motivations, projects, and personal expectations in the next session through the profile map.

Profile maps of Gurus

Based on the Labs' feedback in the co-creation sessions, we identified the competencies of the women who would be the Gurus using the profile map tool. We considered how to associate the characters and interpersonal competencies, which could later be used to generate interdisciplinary exchanges between Gurus, Ambassadors and transfer labs' instructors.

Some of the primary motivations and challenges are (Figures 11, 12)

- Access to technologies and science.
- Intergenerational transmission of their work.
- Raising awareness of environmental issues – A more sustainable and inclusive world.
- Understanding differences and helping to reduce inequalities.
- Understanding the challenge of the lack of natural resources.

Figure 11- Extract from a profile map, fields: "Motivation/Goals/Aspirations" and "Needs/Barriers/Frustrations".

Figure 12 – Comparative extract from another profile map.

Although some of the frustrations are bound up to socio-environmental issues, most of the frustrations and challenges on an individual level relate to activities, time management, and personal life with their profession, including motherhood (Figure. 13), refer as an important point of innovation strategies for reputation management.

Figure 13 – Extract from two profile maps, field: "Needs/Barriers/Frustrations"

Information regarding skills and interests will be processed further in the "next steps", in conjunction with the co-creation session with WP3 and WP2, to understand the Gurus' expertise and generate exchange.

Figure 14 - Extract from two profile maps, Knowledge and Skills.

Another relevant aspect of the skills in different profiles with different expertises and maturity of their work speaks not only about the diversity of the hard skills , but also a key point of the reputation is to shape how these skills are growing and consolidated through the time (Figure 14).

Figure 15 - Extract from four filled profile maps, field: "Your innovation"

Some of the interests and motivations are closely related to some of their lab-related entrepreneurship. In almost all cases, Gurus are women leading the management process in the Lab or are the creators of these spaces or have founded their own brands. It is their driving force for motivation and leadership in a local community (Figure 15). Independently of the field and the results in science (first field), Fashion and sustainability (second field), STEAM education (third field) and Entrepreneurship (fourth field), all converge in the efforts reflected by the lab's engagement.

Figure 16 – Extract from six profile maps, field: “My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry”

In the above maps pictured in Figure 16 we want to summarise an overview that we will consider for further discussion. This information is relevant for the assessment and evaluation WP5 of opportunities and barriers in the textile and clothing industry as well as the women in leadership, and thus to see how these aspects can be changed through the project.

Figure 17 – Extract from two profile maps, field: “Opportunities”

A briefing of the opportunities:

- Learning traditional textile skills in combination with advanced CNC or 3D techniques from fashion and textile industry (first field)
- Need for changemakers (second field)
- Programming
- Interculturality and exchange of countries and languages

Guru Activities

This section proposes a suggestion of activities that we could carry out with the Gurus and will be adjusted in agreement with the Labs and the WP Leaders to fit the needs of Shemakes.eu. These suggested actions will be oriented to support their role as a mentor and link between the local and global communities. Its planning will start in April 2021.

Growth Challenge

This co-creation of growth challenge is about applying the innovation strategies while working on the major challenges facing the clothing and textile industry. This exercise will help us to discover the methods that participants already use in their

maker practices, as well as to empower them to use innovation management tools for the successful development of their activities. e.g; Challenge in Sustainability or inclusivity impact combined with: strategic thinking, SWOTs Time management a.o.

From Gurus to transfer Labs

This activity aims to promote how to engage with and further advise the transfer labs while maintaining innovation standards and collaborate in laboratory standards to enable and prepare the transfer labs for the activities and the welcoming of the Ambassadors. For this reason, the creation of a collaborative training with WP2 and WP3 inputs from the Gurus to the transfer labs is planned.

Some activities are related to help the labs in the doubts and support the process of becoming a transfer Lab. These activities could tackle different topics of staging the lab looking into inventory, machine and equipment distribution. One important aspect is also the engagement of the local community and the mapping of relevant stakeholders and opportunities. The on-boarding sessions are thought to have both a technical approach and a strategic plan to integrate Shemakes activities.

Analysis for entrepreneur innovation skills

The Gurus are active agents as the future experts in Shemakes. Therefore, this analysis aims to support the Ambassador's innovation skills. In lab practices and Fabricademy, programmes are more focused on technology use and skills development and less on innovation methods and techniques. However, innovation skills are part of the "Learning Path" and "Innovation Services" activities. Thus it will be analysed if there is a gap of innovation skills in the current activities and programmes.

We suggest reviewing if the "Learning Path" and "Innovation Services" activities give adequate guidance and training on the following different innovation topics:

1. Innovation management (basics, innovation strategy, culture, processes)
2. Reasoning, problem-solving and ideation (Methods, instruments: Design Thinking, Design Sprint etc.) "Desirability."
3. Business Model Design (Methods, Instrument: Value Proposition Canvas, Business Model Canvas "Viability")

The topics mentioned above are essential innovation competencies which are closely related to the group of "problem-solving" skills which summarises the top skills for jobs in 2025 by the world economic forum Top 10 skills of 2025, World Economic Forum (Figure 18)

(The Future of Jobs Report 2020, 2020).

Top 10 skills of 2025

Source: Future of Jobs Report 2020, World Economic Forum.

Figure 18 – Top 10 skills of 2025. Source: Future of Jobs Report 2020, World Economic Forum

The review could be performed by interviewing participants and trainers or using a survey programme.

If the review shows a gap, there will be recommendations to integrate further innovation skill training in the programmes. Ideas for new training content could be created with the trainers of the “Learning Path” and “Innovation Services” together with the innovation manager of Shemakes.

The training should provide a skill set to develop further ideas and prototypes of the Fabricademy programme to launch new businesses.

Outcomes

One of the outcomes of the reputation strategy activities with the Gurus in the first phase is a plan of the Gurus' actions accompanying the mentoring process of the Ambassadors and the transfer Labs. A documentation of this plan would be ideal to help from the first phase to the second phase when transfer Labs will reproduce their activities.

This documentation is essential to share in the community, foster exchange in the open maker community and ensure sustainability after the Shemakes project.

More details on outcomes will be given in the coming months when we will have more information about implementing the WP2 and WP3 activities. Then we will have a closer idea of the Gurus' first actions and the Ambassadors' selection plan.

3.3 Ambassadors

Ambassadors are participants of Shemakes WP2 and WP3 activities that will be identified through their engagement and exceptional contribution and participation during Shemakes activities. They can also be women profiles from the wider Fabricademy and TCBL network that show interest in the Shemakes project, resonate with its values and want to get involved and contribute to the paths. Ambassadors play a local role in their community because they act as motivators of new activities locally and during their residencies. They also play a global role in the network, bringing knowledge and practices to the transfer Labs.

The Ambassador identification process began with a profile map, with the aim of exploring some of the initiatives, motivations and barriers of the participants and how we could start the selection process.

We have determined 3 Ambassador profile types that address the three target age groups of learning Paths: 12-18, 18-25 and 25+. The profile map will be used during the first stage to start the process of empathisation with the participants and evaluate the development of the competences during the Shemakes activities and the mentoring process.

Figure 19 – Ambassador Profile LEON

We adapted the profile map for the Curiosity target group with the main focus STEAM as the first skills and competences that kids learn. (Figure 19)

Figure 20 – Ambassador Profile REDU

In the Discovery target we identified some of the expertise and Ambassadors' interest in Shemakes activities and in the T&C sector. (Figure 20)

Figure 21 – Profile map IAAC abstract Motivation, Frustration and Interest

Figure 22 – Extract from profile map IAAC, field: "Your innovation", Opportunities, perception TC sector and women in leadership

Figure 23 – Extract from profile map IAAC, field: "Channels"

One of the Ambassadors mentions Cyndy Kohtala (Figure 22), an outstanding leader in academic maker activities, leading several scientific publications in the Fab community. With this example, we can see that women currently very active in the Fablabs network will also join the initiatives and give their testimony in the Shemakes actions. It is also essential to understand what is a role model example for future Ambassadors and how this can help us enrich the vision of Shemakes.

Selection process

Both the selection process and the accompaniment process should be bidirectional between the laboratories and the reputation management, in order to generate circular feedback processes.

The ambassadors will be leading on topics of Sustainability, Industry 4.0, Wearable Tech and Entrepreneurship, as well as engage the community through their motivation, competences and soft skills.

The benefits of being an Ambassador

- The opportunity to travel to transfer Labs to exchange practices.
- Participation in Learning Path activities WP2.
- Participation in innovation activities WP3.
- Access to the Lab for a period of 1-2 weeks.
- Accompaniment of mentoring activities from WP4.
- Cross-collaboration and participation in networking through access to mentoring platforms e.g. Spot.
- Visibility in the media of Shemakes.eu.
- Possibility to participate in fairs and events associated with the Fabricademy/ Fab Foundation e.g: fab conference, TCBL conference.

We see two relevant points in the selection process being their motivation (more details profile map) and the exchanges with the laboratories.

Ambassador's application process

Description

Shemakes offers the opportunity to exchange different competencies between the cross-sectors of fashion, textiles, STEAM and new technologies working on social and environmental impact across these sectors.

Ambassadors will award a residency based on the activities made during the first input from WP2 and WP2. in the first phase, in collaboration with the transfer Labs and the second phase locally in all the Labs network. Ambassadors are encouraged

to extend and promote the learning of SU practices on the four research axes (sustainability, Industry 4.0, wearables Tech and Entrepreneurship). That can generate changes in the perspectives of young entrepreneurs in the local and global community.

Objectives

An application process is important to bring transparency in the Ambassador's selection and stimulate the participation being equal in all Labs, as well as to demonstrate some of the talents and expertise of the Ambassadors that we could discover in the implementation of the Learning Paths or Innovation Services training. This challenge also has the idea of enriching existing practices with new ideas of short time through the initiatives of the challenge participants.

Format

In order to enrich learning exchange, as well as to provide visibility for Ambassadors and for Shemakes on social media, Ambassadors should present their initiative, if relevant, in how-to type tutorials in easy video formats (such as Instagram Reels, which provides a guided way to create 30-second vertical video).

Categories

Categories should be created through the themes that the Learning Paths and Innovation Services impart and assess the impact of the community and the role of women in their context.

Eligibility entry requirements

In this challenge developers, designers, creative people, digital entrepreneurs, makers, and innovative start-ups (only apply to participate in the transfer Labs) that complete at least one of the activities of a Learning Paths or Innovation Service activity successfully, can apply from eligible countries. In principle, it is expected to evaluate the work individually.

For the kids (under 18 years old) format, there will be the possibility to do a virtual exchange as travelling could be a barrier. Overall, COVID restrictions will be followed in the formats for all work packages and proposed activities.

Evaluation criteria

The evaluation will be carried out by the Advisory board during the pitch presentation and a pre-selection by the Gurus. An idea of evaluation criteria could be performed in the following aspects:

- 40% Impact potential (e.g. social, environmental, SDGs)
- 20% Prototype status/tutorials completion (e.g. technological readiness)
- 20% Business/Entrepreneurship potential (e.g. economic potential, market, business model)

This evaluation will be further discussed taking input from the profiles map and the Lab's feedback. Thus, it will be determined in September 2021.

Ambassador's Activities

This section refers to the support activities that will be coordinated from WP4 to support the Ambassadors from the selection process, preparing the residency or the period of residence in the partner Lab or transfer Lab. This activity will be co-created together with the Gurus and the WP leaders to ensure that it aligns with WP2 Learning Paths and the WP3 Innovation Services' objectives.

In this activity, it is proposed to give guidance on how to approach the Lab and its supervisors before, during and after the Ambassador residency tasks: Ambassador activities, communication, networking, as well as the documentation of the experience. What their role, their commitment, and their outreach is like during this process. These activities will be extended in September 2021 and will be given in the next deliverable.

Outcomes

It is essential that Ambassadors are aware of the documentation of their process in git and could be integrated into Fabricademy processes such as Gitlab; all visual material, including interviews and videos, is regulated by WP6.

This documentation plan will be adapted for each of the SU target groups. WP4 in collaboration with WP2 and WP3 will ensure that the target can document the process in a proper way and foster the practices of documentation. This process should be enjoyable and also help the Ambassador to boost their own practices.

Formats as video, printables in Issuu could be a good example of their practices that guarantee the dissemination of the SU results and could be developed prior to selecting the Ambassadors to evaluate and articulate the scope of tasks that they have to achieve.

4. Visibility: Communication and sharing content

Communication is an integral part of this work package; the very concept of role models is that they are only effective if the audience is aware of them. For this reason, the combined work of the task leaders of WP4 and WP6 is to gather, process and diffuse relevant information about role models in a manner appropriate to the target publics determined for each. Social media is the main method used to diffuse reputation management. For the use of social media in the project in general, including a breakdown of available dissemination channels and how they are employed, please see Deliverable 6.1.

4.1 Content production to promote role models

For each type of role model, we will create – or work with the women chosen as role models to support them as they create – different media outputs that will be developed for the range of publics and platforms involved. Requests to receive material from the role models, or for them to produce material for us, must be highly respectful of their time.

The method used for the collection, creation and diffusion of material is as follows:

1. Request for material to be provided is made by email, with a deadline
2. A waiver is attached to ensure that we have permission to use the material they provide to us for the purpose of this work package and for the promotion of the project in general, in any medium
3. Material is shared in the relevant shared Google Drive folder
4. The communications team creates content types as previously determined with the WP4 leader
5. Graphics or videos depicting the role model are circulated to her for approval
6. Material produced is diffused on the appropriate channels.

At the moment, we have determined the content to be produced for the Advisors, who have already been chosen and material has already been requested from them. With the photos and bios we received, we will:

- Make a graphic collage image to promote the Advisor (see D6.1 section 1.3.4)
- Make a 1-minute video with text and image based on her bio
- Hold a live interview streamed, or premiered, on Facebook and YouTube
- Use the information gathered to publish an article on the blog

Interviews with Advisors will be carried out by partners, matching the skills and interests of the partner with the Advisor in order to stimulate a high-level conversation. Interview questions should come out of research by the interviewer following guidelines and including some sample/standard questions provided by the communications team. WP4 and 6 leaders will provide support if needed. Questions should be supplied to interviewees at least 72 hours in advance of the live or recorded event. The event may be live streamed to social media. For those Advisors unable to schedule a live, pre-recordings using in-person technology when available or videos that were recorded remotely using the Streamyard tool will be used.

With regard to Gurus and Ambassadors, their actions and ability to share their learning may be more important than their biographies or business experience, so we expect that the best way to promote them and their work will be through sharing videos. We can imagine short how-to videos for social media formats like Instagram Reels, longer demonstrations for YouTube, written interview articles to highlight their knowledge and skills, etc. Once the selection of these figures is complete, we will customise our requests and content types to fit their unique skills.

4.2 Networking

The exchange and promotion of Gurus and Ambassadors are essential to enrich the contacts' network and give visibility to the project. We recommend the use of a digital mentoring platform, especially considering the difficulties of physical exchange. This platform could be of great benefit for business networking, boosting new entrepreneurs, and offering mentoring possibilities through this space.

In Shemakes WP2- WP3 exchange sessions with the Labs, MAKE shared with WP4 the example of their Spot platform, which we will evaluate the possibility of implementing this exchange through this virtual space.

[Spot](#) by makesense

Through the spot.makesense.org platform, makesense provides thousands of social entrepreneurs with free training, advice, mentors and peer-to-peer support. Over 5000 entrepreneurs have joined the platform over the course of one year, because they find: local networks of innovators, national networks of field-related innovators, experienced professionals willing to give them advice and challenge their ideas, training on specific issues like crowdfunding campaigns, legal matters a.o. All at a distance.

Training

Figure 35 – Extract from the platform “Spot”. ([makesense spot, 2021](#))

Peer to peer support

Figure 36 – Extract from the platform “Spot”. ([makesense spot, 2021](#))

Potential connections between Spot and Shemakes

On the one hand, we could imagine a dedicated Shemakes space in Spot where innovators, Gurus, Ambassadors and businesses could connect. On the other hand, we need to define the features we would ideally like to have if we were to use a platform, then compare it to what Spot can offer. Then, we would need to evaluate the technology behind Spot and see if this is compatible with other existing platforms within Shemakes (we would need to set up a workshop with makesense’s digital team). Finally, we would need to lift the language barrier, since Spot is only available in French, for the time being.

5. Conclusion and outlook

The reputation strategy methodology was built, working together with WP1 Ecosystem opportunities, WP2 Learning Paths and WP3 Innovation Services. This co-creative process helps to identify which aspects are essential to creating the reputation and the best experiences of Shemakes.eu, as well as starting the first dialogues about the meaning of role models and their actions.

As first actions, we issued a summary of the Advisory Board's first meeting identifying their profiles with the identification of the first review of ideas and messages that they want to convey through this project. The activities defined in this document propose an open dialogue with the partners to participate in the elaboration of this strategy and the evaluation of the activities, in synchronisation with the subtasks and the activities of the other packages, bounding the reputation management strategy.

We implemented the profile map tool for the Gurus' first approach, who are already leaders of initiatives in their laboratories and profiles maps of potential Ambassadors.

Through the profiling exercise and the Labs' exchange meetings, activities for the Gurus and the process's outcomes were proposed, outlining a work route for the following months (M4-M9). A framework for Ambassadors has been suggested, and will be enriched, joining activities with Gurus and Ambassadors. Thus, it is expected that the mentoring processes will be dynamically linked between the Reputation Management package with the Gurus, Ambassadors and Labs.

The visibility chapter introduced media activities and how these activities will support the process of disseminating the outcomes, such as the video formats of interviews and the message we intend to communicate as Shemakes (WP6) has been raised. Finally, we mentioned the possibility of exchange and mentoring through digital formats, such as the Spot platform already set up by MakeSense. Necessary adjustments will be made to ensure its successful implementation.

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V 0.2	10.03.2021	A. Cabrera A. Pistofidou	Matrix IAAC	Second draft and table of contents
V 0.3	16.03.2021	N. Lichtenthaler	Matrix	Deliverable before partner review
V 0.4	21.03.2021	A. Pistofidou	IAAC	Proofreading
V 0.5	30.03.2021	A. Cabrera	Matrix	Final draft
V 1.0	31.03.2021	J. Marsh	TCBL	Final edits for delivery

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Glossary

Best practices

"A best practice is an optimal way to achieve a stated goal or objective." The term is defined differently by various organizations. Some say "best practice refers to a consistent way of doing something" or "best practice is simply ensuring that everyone in the project management function uses the same templates and software" (Abudi, 2009). Nevertheless, all definitions describe that the completion of a task is done in a specific and optimal way.

Creating a culture of success

The problems we face today require more than one idea, they require working with other organisations and supporting people to be part of the solution. As important as the process and principles organisations we adopt, is the culture of an organisation and how it connects with citizens and partners³.

Engagement

Engagement is needed with people who are delivering the ideas and receiving them, but also with other partners who might have other ideas. Developing connections and building relationships is as important as creating ideas.

Leadership

Leadership is addressed in SU context as the need to encourage innovation, build skills and capability, provide permission for experimentation and learning. Strong leadership also allows projects to be open and agile, showing results along the way and being able to change.

Individual ecosystems

An individual ecosystem describes the close environment in which the individual operates. In other words, the workplace/work environment, employees, colleagues and company resources. The factors of the environment are linked with the

³ <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/news-opinion/what-framework-innovation-design-councils-evolved-double-diamond>

knowledge and skills of the individual, so that the combination results in an ecosystem.

Innovation ecosystem:

Innovation ecosystems can be described as “a number of symbiotic economic and sociological interactions between actors or entities” (Mattila et al. 2019). Nowadays, Innovation ecosystems have become a core element of the growth strategy of companies in many industries, as the cost of coordinating these systems has been reduced due to information technologies. Ecosystems make it possible to create value that individual companies could not have created on their own (Adner 2006).

Responsible research and innovation

Science and technology gain knowledge, generate well-being and drive development. In addition, science also poses ethical dilemmas, leads to some undesirable effects and generates new challenges. With this kind of progress, great challenges can be overcome and put into a social context (Barbosa, 2019).

STEM education

STEM education means the training of expertise in disciplines of science (S), technology (T), engineering (E), or mathematics (M) (Honey, Pearson and Schwingruber, 2014).

STEM research

This term refers to research fields in science (S), technology (T), engineering (E), or mathematics (M) (Kuschel, 2020).

STEM entrepreneurship

STEM entrepreneurship means to run a business in the field of science (S), technology (T), engineering (E), or mathematics (M). “STEM women entrepreneurs can play an important role as mentors and role models for younger women and thus push girls towards education in these fields” (Poggesi et al., 2020).

STEM to STEAM

STEAM describes the addition of the discipline of “art” to the existing STEM subjects - science, technology, engineering and mathematics. This is intended to create holistic innovations, since STEM disciplines alone are not effective (Maeda, 2013).

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7. Annex I: Advisory Board profiles

In the following, we provide a more in-depth profile for each of the Advisory Board members.

Science and Research

Aurélie Mossé

Aurélie Mossé is a professor in Design for Material Futures & co-head of the Soft Matters research group in Ensadlab, the French pioneering art & design-led research Lab of Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Arts Décoratifs (ENSAD), Paris. Her research practice sits at the intersection of textile design, architecture and new materials & technologies with a focus on exploring how these materials can inform more resilient and poetic perspectives of inhabitation, including working for the shaping of more sustainable creative industries. Her approach is practice-based, always placing making at the centre of the research process, prospective and fundamentally interdisciplinary, favoring the dialogue between design, science and industry. Her PhD thesis entitled 'Gossamer Timescapes: Designing Self-Actuated Textiles for the Home' (2015) explores more specifically the design of three-dimensional dynamic textiles for the home based on photovoltaic, electro-active and light-responsive technologies in collaboration with leading European technical universities including Potsdam (Germany), Eindhoven (Netherlands) and Copenhagen (Denmark). Since then, she has been exploring the boundaries between active materials, bio-digital design and circular design while contributing to international conferences, exhibitions and publications in the area of smart materials, textile & fashion design, architecture and digital crafting. In 2020, she has become an associated member of the Weaving programme of the Matters of Activity Cluster (MoA) at the Humboldt University.

Rebecca Earley

Becky is a design researcher and award-winning research [team leader](#) at University of the Arts London. She is based at Chelsea College of Arts where she is Co-Director of Centre for Circular Design (CCD). In October 2021 she co-founded [World Circular Textiles Day 2050](#) with a team of like-minded collaborators who all want to create clear roadmaps for circular textiles, by drawing together current academic and industry research into inspiring, shared visions.

Becky's practice research encompasses making materials and prototypes, exhibition curation and writing. She is also a highly skilled workshop facilitator and

communicator, specialising in the translation of cross disciplinary design-led research into commercial contexts for sustainable fashion textiles and other fields. She particularly enjoys the challenge of educating and inspiring all kinds of audiences into more sustainable choices and actions towards circular futures.

She trained as a printed textile designer (BA Hons, Loughborough, 1992) and fashion print designer (MA, Central Saint Martins, 1994), before setting up her B.Earley London-based studio in 1995, with support from the Prince's Trust, Arts Council and the Crafts Council. In the late 90's she created her award-winning low-impact, 'exhaust printed' recycled textiles. Her creative fashion textile work has been widely exhibited over the last twenty years; her prints and garments are collected by museums across the globe including [MFIT in New York](#), [RISD Museum](#), as well as the [V&A](#) and [Crafts Council](#) in London and the [Pitt Rivers Museum](#) (Oxford) (Earley, 2021).

Policymaker

Gabriela Macoveiu

Gabriela graduated in 1989 as engineer at the Technical University Ghe. Asachi Iasi. Her experience in business was accumulated by practicing as engineer for 10 years on the Fibrex Nylon Savinesti Chemical Platform; in 2003 she obtained an MBA certificate issued by INCCOR Bucuresti that was successfully used in the field of european programmes management in RDA North-East, where she works since 1999 as regional development manager. During the last 20 years Gabriela coordinated multidisciplinary teams, implemented strategic regional development and smart specialization activities, elaborated and coordinated economic development projects, both for RDA and other similar public authorities and private managers from EU and accessing countries. Her experience as consultant was accumulated by delivering regional development technical assistance and training for RDA North-East, EURECNA CNA Veneto, European Commission Delegation in Yerevan, Assogal Toscana, European Institute for European Policies in Berlin. She is a certified trainer for projects evaluation and strategic management.

Non profit organization

Daniela Toccafondi

Daniela Toccafondi is director of Pratofutura, a non profit association among Prato leading entrepreneurs whose aim is to investigate the future development of the area. Since 1997 she has also been a Lecturer of Applied Economy at the Prato Campus of the Florence University. Since 2007 she is the director of CEDIC, an

Advanced Course in Culture, Economics and Law in the Internationalization Processes Towards China. She has written papers on aspects of the industrialization of the Prato district and on the fashion industry (Smyth & French, 2009).

Silvia Brandi

“Trained as an architect and raised as a manager” – because of her flexible and international profile Silvia Brandi is able to meet different diversified professional challenges. In the last stage of her career in IAAC (Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia), as Director of Marketing and Communications, she drove an important growth process. Later, as managing director, she adapted the necessary reorganization and consolidation of processes to the new size of the organization. Now, as the head of the Atlas of the Future she enjoys raising the value of the people and projects building a better future from all over the world. Silvia Brandi describes herself as a creative and inclusive leader with an optimistic and goal-oriented attitude. She is interested in values-driven organisations and projects with a positive impact on the society (Silvia Brandi, 2021).

Business and Consultancy

Anna Fiscale

Anna Fiscale, born in Verona in 1988, is the Founder and President of [Progetto QUID](#), an Italian social enterprise. She graduated in Economics specializing in Management of Public Administration, International and European Affairs, and travelled a lot to write her thesis and work as an intern in different countries. The will to develop a project that could help people in need and the passion for fashion that she’s had since a young age resulted in the creation of Progetto QUID, an ethical and ecological fashion brand.

The goal, that then became QUID’s social mission, was to help disadvantaged individuals start a new life and regain self-confidence through work.

In 2014 Progetto QUID was awarded first prize in the European Social Innovation Competition, and receiving such an acknowledgment in the international scene made them realise how the potential of our project could easily take them even further than they initially imagined (Boatcamp 2017 | Anna Fiscale, 2017).

Marte Hentschel

Marte Hentschel is a serial entrepreneur, an ideational leader & sustainability expert in platform creation and responsible sourcing with long term experience in co-creation formats, change processes and applying digital technologies to industries

in flux. She is the CEO at Sqetch, speaker, consultant, coach and university lecturer. Sqetch connects fashion brands to manufacturers and suppliers with a B2B sourcing engine and a production management tool.

In addition to digital matchmaking Sqetch curates and organises a range of innovation platforms including hackathons, exhibitions, conferences and think tanks, to catalyse the digital and sustainable transformation of the fashion and textiles industry.

Amber Jae Slooten

Amber Jae Slooten is a fashion designer and works with the body, animation and digital fashion design. Her work questions the way in which we will fit, purchase and wear clothing in the future. She plays with the way in which our digital identity can take shape in VR, AR and MR. Using algorithms, she researches the image and trend analyses of other labels and then creates new (virtual) worlds showing the results. Furthermore, she works together with fashion labels, 3D models, animators, editors and sound designers. Slooten graduated from the Amsterdam Fashion Institute in 2016 and is a co-founder and creative director of The Fabricant, a digital fashion house that uses visual effects from the film industry to shape a new future image of identity (Jae Slooten, 2019).

Mara Balestrini

Mara Balestrini (PhD) is an innovation consultant and Human Computer Interaction (HCI) researcher with more than 10 years of experience in planning and executing innovative digital projects. She currently advises the Inter-American Development Bank on digital transformation. Most recently, Mara was a cabinet advisor to the Secretary of State for Digitalization and Artificial Intelligence of the Government of Spain and CEO of the innovation consultancy Ideas for Change. She is also an adjunct professor at the Institute of Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC) and the Instituto de Empresa (IE). She earned a PhD in Computer Science from the Intel Collaborative Research Institute on Sustainable Connected Cities (ICRI-Cities) at University College London (UCL). She also has a BA in audiovisual communications, a postgraduate degree in media arts, and a MSc in cognitive systems and interactive media. Her work has been awarded in ACM CHI, ACM CSCW, Ars Electronica, among others, and presented in international media such as the BBC, The Guardian, The Financial Times and El País. ('Mara Balestrini', n.d.).

Annex II: Profile Maps

In the following pages we present profile maps for Gurus and Ambassadors.

shemakes Profiles IAAC

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB: IAAC

Avatar: A
Age: 31
Gender:

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **swimming, dancing and walking among**

My favorite color is...: **black**

Career & Background Profession/Function: **Social entrepreneur & Social scientist**

My quotes
"making sustainability matters"

this quote always inspires me
They will not shut us down
Michelle Franco

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

learn and collaborate

My next big challenge in life...

be a mom.

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears, barriers and frustrations

Lack of trust and transparency

hetero-man-white-driven spaces

Lack of time in nature

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...

I work with distributed design, manufacturing, circular economy and social development. My engagement with the community happens via the projects I am involved directly or as practitioner. I also participate in academic networks, especially concerning sustainable development and social cohesion. I make sustainability. I connect, I work, I care.

Opportunities

Expectations
I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

data (e.g. material flow) analysis &

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

re-use **less consumerism** **natural resources and raw materials**

Barriers/needs

political will **to shape the competitive market** **community work**

Trends

CO2 measures from producers to the manufacturing process **Food waste upcycling** **Circular Economy applications for the industry**

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

respect **respect** **respect**

Barriers/needs

tolerance **your quality of leadership not accessible to relevant women** **cultural change**

Trends

interacti onality is important **gender planning and gender stantion** **small business models led by women are not sustainable**

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

Chiamamanda Ngozi Adichie's book and TED talk... "we should all be feminists" - https://www.ted.com/talks/chiamamanda_ngozi_adichie_we_should_all_be_feminists

Introduction to crucial optimism, by Lauren Berlant & DREU Frameworks: https://www.led.ac.uk/artforum/development/issue/barter/flowup/1615.pdf

for me Cindy Kohtala is good leader because she is a great thinker and observer who has been supporting to capture the values of the Maker Movement on fabricating resilience, from an academic perspective, and claiming for sustainability within the MM channels. And Lucy Bernholz, because she has been a driven force for digital civil society security and inclusiveness.

I follow this group, of Precisou Plastics socials, because is a really good example of open, relevant and community-driven platform.

my favorite app the ones I do need to use... xx

Ambassador - IAAC Lab

shemakes Profiles IAAC

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB: IAAC

Avatar: Yellow Electric clown
Age: ..38.
Gender:female..

About me:

Preferences/hobbies **festivals, hiking, traveling, documentaries, art**

My favorite color is... **blue**

Career & Background Profession/Function **Digital Fabrication expert, Instructor, Speaker, Designer, Coordinator**

My quotes
If technology in the western world is taken for granted, crafts are an emergency.

this quote always inspires me
"Call me Trim Tab"
backmaster fuller

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...
 please move the ball in the one(s) you feel identify and add the percentage(%) you think plays for you a role
 Entrepreneur (10%) Visionaire (10%) Architect (10%) Thinker (10%)
 Facilitator (10%) Vision of insights (10%) Strategic plan for everything (10%)
 Adventurer (10%) Entertainer (10%) Executor/leader (10%) Defender (10%) Translator (10%)
 Investor (10%) Teacher (10%) Mentor/consultor (10%)

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

to create a community and a space for people to express their creativity.

My next big challenge in life...

is to make a new laboratory and a house somewhere in the countryside

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears, barriers and frustrations

communication deficit

being judged

limitations in team growing

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...

your answer

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

your answer

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

Barriers/needs

Trends

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

Barriers/needs

Trends

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

this book ...
this article ...
this web ...
other ...

for me (she/he) ... is good leader because ...

I follow this group ... because is a really good example of ...

my favorite apps ...

...

Ambassador - IAAC Lab

shemakes Profiles IAAC

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB: IAAC

Avatar: J
Age: 27
Gender: Non-Binary

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **climb, draw, make, dance, cook**

My favorite color is...: **black**

Career & Background Profession/Function: **Designer and Action Reseacher**

My quotes

"

"

"

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Please move the ball in the ones you feel identify and add the percentage(%) you think pays for you a role

- Entrepreneur: I start something enjoy living on the edge.
- Facilitator: able to implement their roles/ers.
- Visionaire: vision of bringing a team to the goal.
- Architect: designs plan for everything.
- Thinker: critically analyse.
- Adventurer: explore and experience something new.
- Entertainer: life is never boring around them.
- Executor/ maker: practical.
- Defender: advocate for change, warm protectors.
- Translator: provide a space to communicate and create together.
- Investor: eager in solution finding.
- Teacher: mentor, conductor.

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

Being more confident/ accepting with oneself capacity/ capabilities is a challenge and a motivation.

My next big challenge in life...

Having patience, things take time - not everything can be tackled and done in this exact moment.

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional barriers and frustrations

We cannot please everyone at all times, that does not mean that they will simply let us down/ not accept one anymore.

Sometimes I wish I would be more patient with myself and others - working on that

Short answer...

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...

your answer

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

your answer

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

My point of view about woman in leadership

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

this book: Richard Sennet - Together

for me (she/he) Jane Godall is good leader because she cares.

I follow this group jewish intersectionalist, because is a really good example of inclusive approaches

my favorite apps - I dont think I have that

Ambassador - IAAC Lab

shemakes Profiles

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB:

Avatar: ...Member of the makesense organisation (guru).....
 Age:27.....
 Gender:F.....

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **Biking, discovering new exhibitions**
 My favorite color is...: **Orange**
 Career & Background Profession/Function: **> Studied in political science and entrepreneurship**
> Then worked providing training programs for young entrepreneurs in an

My quotes

"I want to share all my positive energy working for a better world."

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

Goal: Making my professional activity a lever to make the world more inclusive and sustainable

My main motivation is to see the blooming of all the beautiful projects with social and environmental impact that I accompany.

My next big challenge in life...

Professionally: to develop more knowledge in entrepreneurship in order to be even more relevant in my project coaching.

Personally: to be able to find a good balance between my professional and personal life so that I have time to invest in associative projects alongside work.

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears, barriers and frustrations

The fear that not enough people are moving towards social entrepreneurship.

A world struggling to move towards greater sustainability

Short answer...

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
 My engagement to the community...
 I make...
 I connect...
 I work...

Through an association in which I am a volunteer, I coordinate workshops helping homeless people to return to work (CV, mock interviews...).

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

Raise awareness and get even more young people on board to make them involve themselves in an impact project, so that they can become the change-makers of tomorrow.

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

Make it more sustainable
 Improve production conditions
 Streamline the manufacturing process so that people consume less

Barriers/needs

people's consumption habits
 the need for profits in this market

Trends

Interest in more sustainable factors (growing awareness)
 Interest & better treatment of the workers in the garment's industry
 Innovation and fashion

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

More women in high positions
 A better representation of women
 more women in decision-making leading

Barriers/needs

Self-censorship
 Ordinary sexism
 Hiring discrimination

Trends

Me too
 Fighting against gender-based violence

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

Book: *Sapiens, a brief history of humankind* by Yuval Noah Harari

for me (she/he) is good leader because.....

I follow this group because is a really good example of

my favorite apps ...

Guru - MAKE SENSE Lab

shemakes Profile MAKE SENSE

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB:

Avatar:Entrepreneur (ambassador)
 Age:23.....
 Gender:F.....

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **Hiking, Yoga**
 My favorite color is...: **Yellow**
 Career & Background Profession/Function: **Business School Consultant in digital transformation**

My quotes

"I want to have a meaningful impact on the world to make it more equal and sustainable, but for this I need your support."

This quote always inspires me
 Success is not measured by the amount of money you make but by the impact you have on people's lives.
 Michelle Obama

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

- Make the world more sustainable
- Connect with people
- Become a changemaker
- Drive a meaningful impact on my community

My next big challenge in life...

Find a way to launch my impact project to help my beneficiaries (ex: find funds, sharpen my vision...)

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears, barriers and frustrations

Need for emotional and financial support

Fear of not gaining enough support for your project

Frustrated that people around her are not sufficiently aware of social and environmental issues.

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
 My engagement to the community...
 I make...
 I connect...
 I work...

Through an association of which I am a volunteer, I have developed a training program to teach women how to code, and thus feminize the world of tech

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

I would like to have a natural leadership talent to get more and more citizens involved in my impact project.

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

ethics local vegan friendly

Barriers/needs

Fast fashion workers condition accessibility

Trends

woman in coding tech and fashion sustainable fashion

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

More women on boards More women CEO & shareholders Safe working conditions

Barriers/needs

glass ceiling self-censorship gendered socialisation

Trends

#me too wage gap sexual harrasment

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

Reclaim, collection of eco-feminist texts by Emilie Hache

for me (she/he) is good leader because.....

I follow this group because is a really good example of

my favorite apps ...
 ...

Ambassador - MAKE SENSE Lab

shemakes Profiles ONLF

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB:

Avatar: ELSA
Age: 65
Gender: WOMAN

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **knitting, cooking, woodworking**
My favorite color is...: **Red**
Career & Background Profession/Function: **retired university professor (physics or engineering)**

My quotes

"I don't like labels and I don't like ghettos: I prefer thinking about humanity rather than women and men"

"Even in a world that's being shipwrecked, remain brave and strong."
background of design

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

Use my free time to do something stimulating for me and useful for the others

My next big challenge in life...

Support the Feb Lab

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears, barriers and frustrations

Be as sharp as I used to be

No time to waste to defend my competences

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...

I'd like to hack an old Brother that I used in the 90s.

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

Sweaters for my grandchildren using a digital knitting machine

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

Technology for creativity

Barriers/needs

Still too traditional Little evolution

Trends

#software

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

Women in technology and science benefit the other fields as well

Barriers/needs

Being multitasking doesn't help to become a leader Interest to dedicate time to families

Trends

#diversity

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

This is a text box...

for me Angela Merkel is good leader because she has the authority

I like Adafruit site, because is a really good example of teaching and explaining

my favorite apps

Ambassador - ONLF Lab

shemakes Profiles

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB:

Avatar: Cristina
Age: 43.
Gender: female

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **Nature and reading**

My favorite color is...: **black**

Career & Background Profession/Function: **Physicists - Science Education and communication - Fab Lab manager**

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...

My engagement in science democratisation and education since I was a university student. Proud to have co-founded an open Fab Lab

My quotes
Work hard & be nice to people

the quote always inspire me
Ask and it will be given to you; seek and you will find; knock and the door will be opened to you. For everyone who asks and receives, the one who seeks finds; and to the one who knocks, the door will be opened

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

Give opportunities to those who don't have. Especially in science and technology.

My next big challenge in life...

Develop On'l'fait and the MACO

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears, barriers and frustrations

work-life balance

engage the people I work with

Miss opportunities

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Opportunities

Expectations
I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

programming

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

My point of view about women in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

**this book ...
this article ...
this web ...
other ...**

for me Angela Merkel is good leader because she's a physicist, pragmatic and authoritative.

I follow Adafruit, because is a really good example of teaching

my favorite apps

Guru - ONLF Lab

shemakes Profiles

Opportunity ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB: REDU

Avatar: Andreea Sofronea - GURU
Age: 35
Gender: F

About me:

Preferences/hobbies

Theatre, movies, Fashion - Design, sewing, reading, movies, crafts, DIY, muuuuic

My favorite color is...

Prussian Blue

Career & Background

Bachelor Degree in Theatre Acting, Masters Degree in Theatrical Arts, co- manager at REDU, Product manager, project support staff at Mai bine NGO

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...

My soul project is REDU, and even though it did not start on my initiative, I believe that it became pretty much my/our own. Founded on a very ambitious idea (transforming textile waste into new products), it didn't receive much credit in the beginning especially in terms of projects market sustainability. From its beginning REDU was that kind of place where everything I did, made, no matter how many hour I spent in the atelier, I enjoyed it and it didn't seem like work. We used to be 5 involved in the team, now we're just 2 people, both bringing our best in every activity from sewing, designing, prototyping, social media, educating and organising local events with topics form our area of interest. There are other soul projects but those are mostly on the performance - theatre - area in which I managed to remain active in the past 12 years.

My quotes

"The only constant is change."

Not a quote but a poem
Everybody is free to wear
sunscreen
- Buzz Luermans

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

We cannot have unlimited growth as long as the planet's resources are limited. Mostly the motivation behind the REDU project and Mai bine Organisation with all their inputs and activities in the community.

My next big challenge in life...

To turn it up the challenge consists out of three eu projects in which I'm involved for the next 4 years, on top of them REDU and a Zero waste Shop we're opening these days. I still can't believe it's happening - it's a dream come true and an anxiety starter pack at the same time. :)

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears barriers and frustrations

- Burnout
- Time seems to never be enough
- Babies

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

I wish I could organise my time better between projects and activities. I also wish to learn how to operate a 3D pattern making cad soft- this is something I would definitely like to do astonishingly well. I would love to spend some time in the workshop with Elvys and make a new REDU collection.

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

Circularity locally produced garments Sustainability

Barriers/needs

A very grounded linear production line More educated and informed clients

Trends

computers are indispensable by nature (read it in a magazine I had it suitable here)

My point of view about women in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

Diversity in leadership Diminished wage gap Empowering women

Barriers/needs

genderless education- grass roots approach Model is main associated to men. But concept itself created a masculine image.

Trends

#me too #banning bossy #pay your workers

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

this book THE COMPLETE COSTUME HISTORY, A. Racinet REWORK, David Heinemeier & Jason Fried, Human Ecology Guide, A.E. Gheorghicã

for me Anca Gheorghicã, also my colleague, is good leader because she

I follow this group..... because is a really good example of

my favorite apps: machinarium (game), puzzle games, Instagram

Guru- REDU Lab

shemakes Profile REDU

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB:

Avatar:
 Age:25.....
 Gender:woman.....

About me:

Preferences/hobbies **ecology activist, diy craft, music, art, all things new, out and about**

My favorite color is... **turquaz**

Career & Background Profession/Function **Art University graduate, management courses graduate, internship at a marketing company/entry level creative job**

My quotes

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

Eager to learn, Being part of the generation that had a big impact on diminishing the gender gap. Be

My next big challenge in life...

Be resilient to the upcoming changes in the world.

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears barriers and frustrations

Loss of energy, patience and involvement as you get older

Lack of time due to doing these activities alongside a full time job

Not resonating with same age groups ideas and interests

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
 My engagement to the community...
 I make...
 I connect...
 I work...

My engagement to the community was creating a Facebook Group where people could swap/trade objects, clothes or services between themselves without using money. The value was expressed in time offered/bargained for a specific item. The services offered have to be a skill that they are good at or that they enjoy doing. The group is also a place for sharing news, ideas, experiences regarding sustainability, circularity and ecology. I managed to gather around 200 people, all from my local town. And once in a while I also organize a physical event with the same theme.

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

Run an ethical, sustainable, close to zero waste, circular fashion brand that sets new standards in the T&C sector.

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

to reduce its waste

to become locally sourced and made

stop following trends

regulations from the EU

lack of transparency and traceability

Trends

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

teams formed only of women

no payment gaps related to gender

gender-less jobs

99.99% man leaders

low paid jobs associated only to women

Trends

#pay-your-workers

#who-made-my-clothes

fridays for future

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

Limits to growth - Donella Meadows, Jorgen Randers, Dennis Meadows

for me (she/he) Marina Abramovic is good leader because she chaged the perception of women in arts, she was courageous, outrageous, consequent, brilliant.

I follow this group. CleanClothes Campaign, because it is a really good example of activism on garment workers rights.

my favorite apps: Instagram, Facebook, Books :D

Ambassador - REDU Lab

shemakes Profile WAAG

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB: WAAG

Avatar:
Age: 33
Gender: FEMALE (SHE/HER)

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **YOGA / NATURE / FESTIVALS**

My favorite color is...: **THE FULL RAINBOW**

Career & Background Profession/Function

Studied business administration, worked as a product manager for a big fashion retailer for many years, and later founded her own fashion brand. Moved from Brazil to Amsterdam in 2018, and in 2019 she kicked off her journey into a creative multi-disciplinary design path by researching innovative biomaterials and digital fabrication techniques joining Fabricademy course. Since September 2020 she joined TextileLab Amsterdam as a designer and concept developer to work on multiple projects.

My quotes

"..."

the quote always inspires me

Author

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

My personality Assertive Campaigner

As a leader, I can be ...

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

TO LEARN AND DISCOVER NEW POSSIBILITIES, MAKE A CONTRIBUTION TO A WORLD WITH LESS SOCIAL INEQUALITY, MAKE A CONTRIBUTION TO A BETTER ECOSYSTEM, PRESERVE THE NATURAL WORLD, CREATE SOMETHING WITH OTHER PEOPLE AND UNDERSTAND DIFFERENT POINT OF VIEWS

My next big challenge in life...

how to balance personal and professional life, to keep developing personal projects and engaging with things I'm interested in, without undermining life quality

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears, barriers and frustrations

Too much work for too little time

Trying to always deliver when is not always possible

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...

On my work at Waag I see the opportunity to bring my previous experience with the global fashion industry and also as an entrepreneur, connecting those worlds with the ones from Fabricademy and projects like SheMakes. I believe that not being an artist/designer by education allows me to have a more holistic/systematic approach to innovation, and to have a more "down to earth/pragmatic" view as well.

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

Learn more on traditional fashion skills, pattern making, sewing, knitting, weaving...

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

be more open collaborative
less glamour and luxury
local for local

Barriers/needs

how to be sustainable and still economically viable
Understand the problem from inside the industry to propose solutions

Trends

social responsibility/transparency
environmental sustainability
valuing hand-craft

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

demand equal rights
recognition and respect by the society

Barriers/needs

self-confidence
improve soft skill set

Trends

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

this book ...
this article ...
this web ...
other ...

for me (she/he) is good leader because.....

I follow this group because is a really good example of

my favorite apps ...

...

Guru - WAAG Lab

shemakes Profiles

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB: LEON

Avatar: ...NURIA.....
Age: ...51.....
Gender: ..FEMALE.....

About me:

Preferences/hobbies **CALLIGRAPHY, FASHION DESIGN**
My favorite color is... **PINK**
Career & Background Profession/Function **MECHANICAL ENGINEER**

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

My quotes

"...PLAY IS THE HIGHEST FORM OF RESEARCH".
EINSTEIN
"We often treat children as if they're not very competent to do anything on their own. So we make them stop learning in a natural way - by exploring".
S. HALPERT

"IF YOU WANT TO LEARN ANYTHING YOU JUST HAVE TO BE SURE YOU WANT TO DO IT".
Author: TINI, MY GRANDMA

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

I WOULD LOVE TO SEE THE FABLAB FULL OF BOYS AND GIRLS SMILING, COLLABORATING IN THE SAME PROJECTS REGARDLESS OF SEX OR ORIGIN, AND CARING ABOUT HOW TO IMPROVE THE WORLD

My next big challenge in life...

TIME PASSES SO FAST THAT I WOULD LIKE TO TRAIN THE NEXT GENERATION WHO CAN TRANSMIT TO GIRLS AND BOYS MY SAME PASSION FOR TEACHING AND FOR MAKING EVERY CHILD MIND SHINE.

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional barriers and frustrations

INSECURITY

ENGLISH

TIME

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us
My project...PODEROSAS "MAKING THE HARD EASY"
My engagement to the community...FABLAB LEON
I make...
I connect...
I work...

PODEROSAS BORN AS A WAY TO TEACH GIRLS EASILY WHAT HAD SEEMED DIFFICULT TO ME. I CAN DO IT THROUGH FABLAB LEON, A DIGITAL FABRICATION SPACE OPEN TO PUBLIC OF ALL AGES

Opportunities

Expectations
I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

BE ABLE TO SHARE MY EXPERIENCE IN ANY CULTURE, ANY LANGUAGE, ANY COUNTRY

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

study of new materials for clothes

Barriers/needs

trend in changing continuous by continuous need to be informed of the latest trend

Trends

e.g. woman in fashion tech tech innovation

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

equal recognition

Barriers/needs

improvement of qualification conditions

Trends

e.g. #me too remote work

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests
this book: THE ALQUEMIST
this article: ...
this web: thesofircircuiteer.net
other ...

for me (she/he) is good leader because.....

I follow this group because is a really good example of

my favorite apps INSTAGRAM ...

Guru - LEON Lab

shemakes Profile LEON

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB: LEON

Avatar: ..ALI.....
 Age:17.....
 Gender:FEMALE.....

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **CODING**

My favorite color is...: **PINK**

Career & Background Profession/Function:

My quotes
 "We will remove the broccoli of the pizza"

This quote always inspires me
 "Understand well as I may, my infinitesimal fraction of all I want to understand"
 Add LoveNotes

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

Science: Could you give us some details? skills: _____

Technology: skills: **ARDUINO**

Engineering: skills: _____

Art: skills: _____

Math: skills: **CRYPTOGRAPHY**

Others: skills: _____

My personality

Extraverted Introverted

Thinking Feeling

Intuitive Observant

Judging Perceiving

Assertive Turbulent

As a leader, I can be ...

please move the ball in the ones you feel identify and add the percentage(%) you think plays for you a role

Entrepreneur Facilitator Visionaire Architect Thinker

Adventurer Entertainer Executor Defender Translator

Investor Teacher

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

Use knowledge (cybsc) to help others

My next big challenge in life...

University

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears barriers and frustrations

fear to fail

not enough time

Short answer...

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Sustainability: interest: _____

Fashion Tech: interest: **WEARABLES**

Industry 4.0: interest: _____

Entrepreneurship: interest: _____

Mentoring: interest: _____

Health Tech: interest: **DESIGN FOR ALL**

Arts & Crafts: interest: _____

Others: interest: _____

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
 My engagement to the community...
 I make...
 I connect...
 I work...

I'm the founder of a programming group called: "There is a broccoli in my pizza"

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

express myself

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

CREATING SMART CRESSES

Barriers/needs

Trends

e.g. I'm coding

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

INSPIRING GIRLS

Barriers/needs

CARING FOR CHILDREN

Trends

e.g. I'm too

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

50 Fearless Women Who Made History

for me (she/he) ... is good leader because...

I follow this group ... because is a really good example of

my favorite apps: INSTAGRAM, GITHUB

Ambassador -LEON Lab

shemakes Profiles

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

LAB: FabLab Kamp-Lintfort

Avatar: Alessa
Age: 25
Gender: Female

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **photography, cooking, traveling, sightseeing, handcraft, creating and developing**

My favorite color is...: **black, olive green, lilac**

Career & Background Profession/Function: **Media & Communication Computer Science, Project Assistant, FabLab Assistant, Maker/Creator, Webdesigner, Coaching**

My quotes
"You never know what someone is going through, so always be kind."
"Do things and be with people that make you happy."
"Fail, but never give up."
"Don't let anyone tell you that you can't do it."
"It is what it is."

the quote always inspire me
"Be the change you want to see in the world."
-Mahatma Gandhi

Knowledge and skills

I'm particularly good at:

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

please move the ball in the one(s) you feel identify and add the percentage(s) you think plays for you a role

Role	Percentage
Entrepreneur spirit, who truly enjoy living on the edge	10%
Facilitator able to reassure their listeners	70%
Visionaire vision of things & learn to the go	85%
Architect strategic plan for everything	90%
Thinker critically analyse	95%
Adventurer explore and experience something new	10%
Entertainer life is never boring ensure them	10%
Executor/ initiator proactive	10%
Defender advocate for change when protectors	10%
Translator enable a space to communicate and create together	90%
Inventor eager in solution finding	10%
Teacher mentor conductor	10%

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations

Creating a Product/Developing a Business, inspire people to think bigger

My next big challenge in life...

Bachelorthesis, Building a house

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations

Some personal and professional fears barriers and frustrations

Frustration: Perfection, Time

Fear of failing in relationships and personal set goals

...

Interest

I'm particularly interested in:

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us

My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...

→ Building Machines: <https://alessandracrotty.gitlab.io/fabmachine/assignments/11.%20Final%20Project/>, → Fab Academy Projects <https://fabacademy.org/2019/labs/kamp lintfort/students/alessandracrotty/>, Future Work → Robot Kit for Kids, Prototyp Intelligent Orthosis

Opportunities

Expectations

I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...

design products, artificial itelligence, robotics

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry

Opportunities/wishes

Reusable Materials, Multi-functional clothes, Color Changing Clothes

Barriers/needs

Fairtrade, Transparency, CO2 Reduction

Trends

Wearable tech, Robotics, Fairtrade

My point of view about woman in leadership

Opportunities/wishes

Gender Equality, More Women with Support Women, Stop Sexism

Barriers/needs

Gender Equality, Stop Sexism, More Women with Support Women

Trends

Women together

Channels - networking group

the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests

You Goal, Girl - Melissa Bowles

for me (she/he) is good leader because.....

I follow this group. Iridays for future, because is a really good example of social movement

my favorite apps ...

...

Ambassador -Transfer Lab - Kamp Lintfort

shemakes Profiles

Opportunity Ecosystems Bridging the Gender Gap

Katty Fashion SME

Avatar:
Age: 51
Gender: Female

About me:

Preferences/hobbies: **MUSIC, READING and TRAVELING**
My favorite color is...: **PASTEL COLOURS**
Career & Background Profession/Function: **T&C ENGINEER with over 25 years experience in bespoke services of design, product development and womenswear high end manufacturing, currently Founder and CEO of KF an innovative SME and and sustainable development of fashion sector NGO**

My personality

As a leader, I can be ...

Your innovation

A project/initiative that you want to share with us
My project...
My engagement to the community...
I make...
I connect...
I work...
KARE-digitally enabled zero waste resources design, product development and smart&circular garment manufacturing to Fashion Factory of the Future.

My quotes
Let's all think with today actions what we leave for generation to come!
Always look gratefully ,on the correct side of life !

this quote always inspires me
"Nature gives you the face you have at twenty. Life shapes the face you have at thirty. But at fifty you get the face you deserve."
COCO CHANEL

Motivation / Goals / Aspirations
Build a really sustainable and ethical future to all worthwhile around me
My next big challenge in life...
Real awareness of best choices personally and professionally .

Needs / Barriers / Frustrations
Some personal and professional fears, barriers and frustrations
perfectionism
self overloading with others "bagage"
lagging region we belong to

Opportunities
Expectations
I wish I could do the following astonishingly well...
I wish to fulfill my meaning in this life and inspire for doing things the best possible and with care for each other.

My point of view about the textiles & clothing industry
Opportunities/wishes: T&C as strategic sector, better linking between stakeholders, ethical and beneficial for all fashion value chain.
Barriers/needs: updated knowledge skills and competences, access to latest technological developments, real sustainable value chains.
Trends: digitisation, smart manufacturing.

My point of view about woman in leadership
Opportunities/wishes: Better representativity in decision making.
Barriers/needs: Agile Management.
Trends: [empty boxes]

Channels - networking group
the book or article that leads you to your goals, which best reflects your interests: **this book Sustainable Fashion this web McKinsey&Company other BOF Reports ,...**
for me: **Ellen McArthur is good leader because she increased the awareness and even the implementation of sustainable paradigm change**
I follow this group. **SheMakes, because is a really good example of care..**
my favorite apps ...audible, ...

Advisory Board - TCBL Lab

